

Multinationals' Responses to Anti-Base Erosion and Profit Shifting Policies: Evidence from Tax Returns*

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Abstract

Using Austrian administrative corporate tax return data, we examine how MNEs respond to three major anti-base erosion and profit shifting (anti-BEPS) policies: (i) interest and royalty deduction limitations, (ii) private Country-by-Country Reporting (CbCR), and (iii) controlled foreign corporation (CFC) rules. We find that limits on interest and royalty deductions curb income shifting out of Austria, with little evidence that exposed MNE entities substitute into alternative shifting channels. In contrast, private CbCR largely offsets these effects, while also incentivizing MNEs to increase economic activity in foreign low-tax affiliates. Exposure to the CFC rule similarly leads MNEs to increase economic activity abroad and continue income shifting, consistent with efforts to qualify for active-income safe harbors under the Austrian regime. Overall, our evidence suggests that anti-BEPS measures have nuanced effects. Some measures effectively constrain income shifting, whereas others primarily induce real economic responses without reducing the extent of income shifting.

Keywords: Income Shifting, Tax Avoidance, Anti-BEPS Policies, Administrative Tax Data

JEL Classification: H25, H26, F23

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1 Introduction

To curb tax-motivated income shifting by multinational enterprises (MNEs), the OECD launched the Base Erosion and Profit Shifting (BEPS) Action Plan in 2015. The initiative introduced a set of measures designed to limit the relocation of taxable income from high-tax to low-tax jurisdictions (OECD, 2013, 2015). A decade later, the fight against income shifting remains central to international tax policy, as reflected in the BEPS 2.0 project and the introduction of the global minimum tax (OECD, 2021). Yet despite the widespread adoption of anti-BEPS measures, there is limited evidence on whether these policies effectively reduce income shifting or instead induce firms to substitute toward alternative tax-planning strategies or adjust their real economic activities. Answering these questions is important given the substantial political capital invested in the BEPS project, the potentially large revenue losses associated with income shifting, and growing efforts to streamline anti-BEPS rules, including the European Commission’s recent proposals to simplify the EU Anti-Tax Avoidance Directive (ATAD).¹

Prior empirical work largely analyzes individual anti-BEPS measures in isolation and typically focuses either on income-shifting responses or other responses, such as adjustments to real economic activity. Existing evidence is therefore fragmented and often mixed. With respect to private Country-by-Country reporting (CbCR), for example, Joshi (2020) finds no reduction in income shifting in the short run, whereas Adams (2024) documents a significant decrease using a longer sample period. Using U.S. administrative data, Nessa et al. (2025) similarly find little evidence that CbCR reduces income shifting. The evidence on controlled foreign corporation (CFC) rules is somewhat more conclusive, with studies documenting reduced profits reported in low-tax affiliates following their introduction (e.g., Clifford, 2019). However, rather than

¹On June 24, 2026, the European Commission released a proposal for a tax simplification package, including changes to the CFC regime codified in the ATAD. For more details, see EU Commission (2026). The results of this study directly inform these policy efforts.

constraining income shifting consistent with policy objectives, MNEs could respond to anti-BEPS policies through other adjustments. For example, MNEs may substitute toward alternative income-shifting channels not directly targeted by a given policy (Saunders-Scott, 2015; Nicolay et al., 2017). They could also adjust economic activity to substantiate low-taxed profits and maintain tax benefits (De Simone and Olbert, 2022; Rechbauer et al., 2026; Gschossmann and Pfrang, 2024). Evaluating individual measures or examining specific MNE responses in isolation could therefore provide an incomplete picture of a policy’s overall effects. This limitation is particularly important because anti-BEPS measures were largely introduced as part of a coordinated international reform package, implying that MNEs’ responses to one policy might depend on the presence of others.

We contribute to this debate by using Austrian administrative corporate tax return data to analyze and compare the effects of three major anti-BEPS measures: (i) limitations on the deductibility of interest and royalty payments, (ii) private CbCR, and (iii) CFC rules. Importantly, we examine whether these measures primarily reduce cross-border income shifting or instead induce other adjustments, such as substitution across shifting channels and real economic responses. Our findings highlight that not all anti-BEPS measures uniformly constrain cross-border income shifting. Instead, their specific design can induce incentives to substitute toward less affected shifting channels and to adjust economic activity in low-tax jurisdictions.

The Austrian setting is particularly well-suited to address our research questions because Austria has introduced the three anti-BEPS policies in a staggered fashion during our sample period while maintaining a constant statutory corporate income tax rate of 25%. This setting provides a unique opportunity to analyze and compare multiple anti-BEPS measures within the same tax system and to isolate the effects of policy design from broader changes in income-shifting incentives, such as changes in local tax rates. Although all three policies are intended to reduce the incentives for MNEs to shift income out of Austria to lower-taxed foreign affiliates (outward income

shifting), they differ in design and scope, targeting either specific shifting channels (e.g., interest or royalty payments) or shifting incentives more broadly. The staggered introduction of these policies further allows us to study their relative effectiveness and potential interactions within a single institutional environment. An additional advantage of our setting is the availability of administrative corporate tax return data, which mitigates concerns that income-shifting estimates based on financial statement data are biased by tax-exempt dividend income (Amberger et al., 2026; Blouin and Robinson, 2025).

To identify MNE responses to each anti-BEPS measure, we conduct several difference-in-differences (DiD) tests that compare Austrian MNE entities exposed to a given policy with entities whose shifting incentives remain unaffected. Our primary control group consists of entities with inward-shifting incentives (Cristea and Nguyen, 2016), i.e., entities that belong to MNE groups whose lowest foreign statutory corporate income tax rate exceeds the Austrian tax rate. For these entities, the introduction of anti-BEPS measures in Austria does not alter the incentives to shift income out of Austria. We tailor both the treatment definition and the estimation window to the institutional features of each policy. For each test, we define treatment status based on an Austrian entity’s ex-ante exposure to the policy rather than actual treatment so that our empirical strategy closely resembles an intention-to-treat design.

Our empirical analysis combines four complementary data sources. First, we use administrative corporate tax return data from the Austrian Ministry of Finance available through the Austrian Micro Data Center (AMDC). Second, we merge unconsolidated financial statement data from Bureau van Dijk’s Orbis Historical Database. Third, we use administrative foreign affiliate statistics from the AMDC, which cover both inward (IFATS) and outward (OFATS) investment relationships. These data allow us to identify MNE group structures and to construct treatment and control groups for our DiD analyses. Finally, we supplement these data with unconsolidated financial statement data from Bureau van Dijk’s Sabina database, which provides more granular financial

statement information for Austrian entities than standard Orbis data.

Our first set of analyses examines the interest and royalty deduction limitation introduced in 2014. This rule denies the tax deductibility of intra-group interest and royalty payments made by Austrian MNE entities to foreign affiliates subject to tax rates below 10%. We find that taxable income reported by exposed Austrian MNE entities increases by 133% relative to control entities following the reform, corresponding to an economically meaningful increase of approximately EUR 4.6 million per entity-year at the sample mean. These results are robust to matching treated and control entities on observable pre-reform characteristics. To strengthen identification, we conduct a placebo test using Austrian MNE entities whose lowest-taxed foreign affiliate faces a statutory tax rate between 10% (the threshold for the deduction limitation) and 25% (the Austrian statutory corporate tax rate) as a pseudo-treatment group. These entities have incentives to shift income out of Austria, but are not directly exposed to the policy. We find no significant change in taxable income using this pseudo-treatment group, alleviating concerns that our results are driven by differences between MNE entities with inward- and outward-shifting incentives rather than by the policy itself.

An event-study design shows that treated and control entities exhibit parallel pre-treatment trends in taxable income, mitigating concerns about violations of the parallel trends assumption (Roberts and Whited, 2013). We also observe that the effects of the deduction limitation emerge immediately after its implementation in 2014. Additional analyses provide little evidence of alternative adjustment responses. In particular, exposed MNEs do not appear to substitute toward alternative income-shifting channels, such as transfer-pricing manipulation, to compensate for the limited deductibility of intra-group interest and royalty payments. Overall, these findings suggest that restrictions on the deductibility of interest and royalty payments—two rather flexible shifting channels (Hopland et al., 2018)—can effectively constrain income shifting.

We next examine the introduction of private CbCR in 2016. This policy requires

large MNEs to privately disclose detailed country-by-country information on their global operations to domestic tax authorities, which then exchange this information with foreign tax authorities. By expanding tax authorities' information sets and facilitating more targeted audits, private CbCR should indirectly reduce the incentives for income shifting (Joshi, 2020). Consistent with Nessa et al. (2025), however, we find no significant increase in taxable income reported by exposed Austrian MNE entities following the reform. Instead, the extent of income shifting largely reverts back to its pre-2014 level, i.e., the period before the introduction of the interest and royalty deduction limitation. To examine potential interactions between the two anti-BEPS policies, we analyze the evolution of income shifting around the adoption of both policies using an event-study framework. We find that the reduction in income shifting of exposed Austrian MNE entities in response to the deduction limitation does not persist after the introduction of private CbCR. Rather, income shifting gradually returns toward levels observed before either policy was implemented.

To better understand this pattern, we examine potential alternative responses to private CbCR. Our results indicate that exposed MNEs increase employment in foreign low-tax affiliates following its introduction, consistent with them expanding real economic activity abroad to substantiate income shifting. Hence, unlike targeted anti-BEPS measures aimed at specific shifting channels, broader transparency-based policies, such as private CbCR, appear less effective in constraining income shifting. Instead, such policies may induce real economic responses that facilitate income shifting.

Our final set of tests examines the introduction of the CFC rule in 2019. This rule requires certain passive income earned by foreign low-tax affiliates, such as interest and royalty income, to be included in the Austrian parent's taxable income on a current basis. This provision should reduce incentives to shift income abroad and subsequently repatriate it as tax-exempt dividend income. Importantly, the CFC rule does not apply if the low-tax affiliate generates sufficient active business income (active-income safe harbor) or demonstrates sufficient economic substance (substance-based exemption).

Contrary to the policy objective of limiting income shifting, we find that exposed Austrian MNE entities report significantly *lower* taxable income following the reform. These results suggest that the CFC rule facilitates rather than constrains outward income shifting. One explanation is that active-income and substance-based exemptions as included in the Austrian CFC regime reduce residual uncertainty associated with aggressive income shifting. By providing clear thresholds for exemption from the CFC rule, these carve-outs may lower enforcement risk and hence reduce the expected costs of shifting income to low-tax affiliates. Consistent with this notion, we find that exposed MNEs report higher sales in foreign low-tax affiliates following the reform, suggesting that MNEs expand active business activity abroad in order to qualify for CFC exemptions. Overall, the evidence is consistent with MNEs strategically exploiting active-income safe harbors in CFC rules to maintain or even increase income shifting.

Our study contributes to the academic and policy debate on the effects of anti-BEPS measures in several ways. First, we provide an analysis of three major anti-BEPS measures introduced within a single institutional environment. Prior studies largely examine individual policies in isolation (Joshi, 2020; Adams, 2024; Saunders-Scott, 2015) and typically explore income-shifting responses or other adjustments separately. As a result, existing evidence provides a fragmented view of how differences in policy design shape MNE responses and how different anti-BEPS measures might interact. By analyzing targeted anti-BEPS measures, broader transparency-based policies, and measures containing active-income safe harbors, we show that these measures have distinct effects. Whereas some measures effectively constrain income shifting, others primarily induce real economic responses without reducing overall income shifting. Moreover, our results indicate that responses to one policy can attenuate the effectiveness of others. For example, the increase in economic activity abroad following the introduction of private CbCR appears to facilitate income shifting and thereby offsets the initial reduction induced by the interest and royalty deduction limitation.

Second, our study adds to research on substitution across shifting channels.

Saunders-Scott (2015) documents substantial substitution toward royalty payments and transfer-pricing manipulation in response to the introduction of interest deduction limitations. We extend this literature by showing that measures targeting both intra-group interest and royalty payments effectively limit MNEs' ability to substitute toward less flexible channels, such as transfer-pricing manipulation.

Third, we add to research on the effects of transparency-based anti-BEPS policies and rules that contain specific exemptions and carve-outs. Prior studies on private CbCR report mixed evidence on its effectiveness in curtailing income shifting (Nessa et al., 2025; Adams, 2024; Joshi, 2020) while others document real economic responses (De Simone and Olbert, 2022). We complement this literature by directly linking real economic adjustments in low-tax affiliates to continued income shifting. Hence, heterogeneity in MNEs' ability to make such adjustments can explain mixed evidence on the effectiveness of private CbCR. We also add to the literature on CFC rules. While prior work has focused on tax-rate thresholds or substance-based exemptions (Rechbauer et al., 2026; Gschossmann and Pfrang, 2024; Clifford, 2019), we find that MNEs also exploit active-income safe harbors to maintain or even increase income shifting.

More broadly, our evidence suggests that not all anti-BEPS measures uniformly curb income shifting. In fact, their design can provide incentives to substitute across shifting channels or to adjust real economic activity. These findings contribute to current policy debates on the future of international tax policy, with particular relevance for the implementation of the global minimum tax and recent initiatives to simplify anti-BEPS policies in the EU (EU Commission, 2026).

2 Setting and Institutional Background

We use Austria as our empirical setting because it implemented three major anti-BEPS policies in a staggered fashion during our sample period: (i) a limitation on interest

and royalty deductions in 2014, (ii) private CbCR in 2016, and (iii) a CFC rule in 2019. Although all three measures are intended to curb income shifting, in particular income shifting out of Austria, they differ in design and scope and therefore operate through distinct channels. The interest and royalty deduction limitation directly restricts deductible payments to low-tax foreign affiliates. Private CbCR increases transparency and expands the information available to tax authorities, thereby facilitating more targeted tax audits. Finally, the CFC rule taxes certain foreign low-tax passive income at the Austrian parent level, thereby reducing the tax benefits of shifting income abroad.

2.1 Interest and Royalty Deduction Limitation

In 2014, Austria introduced a limitation on the deductibility of interest and royalty payments between affiliated MNE entities. Under §12 (1) Z 10 of the Austrian Corporate Income Tax Act (*Körperschaftsteuergesetz*, KStG), such payments are non-deductible for the paying entity if they are taxed at less than 10% at the recipient entity.² The provision was enacted on February 24, 2014 and became effective on March 1, 2014.³

By denying deductions for payments to foreign low-tax affiliates, the rule directly increases the cost of shifting income out of Austria through intra-group financing and royalty arrangements. To the extent that the policy effectively constrains such income shifting, Austrian MNE entities exposed to the provision should report higher taxable income following its implementation.

²The threshold is generally determined based on the statutory corporate income tax rate applicable to the recipient entity. However, if the recipient entity benefits from a tax exemption or preferential tax treatment (e.g., a refund or a similar relief), the relevant benchmark is the effective tax rate. For tax years beginning on or after January 1, 2026, the threshold increases to 15%, aligning the rule with the global minimum tax rate under the OECD Pillar Two framework.

³After our sample period, Austria also implemented an earnings-stripping rule based on Article 4 of the ATAD. Effective January 1, 2021, net interest deductions are capped at 30% of EBITDA, with an exemption for interest expenses up to EUR 3 million. Unlike the 2014 rule, the earnings-stripping provision applies irrespective of whether the lender is affiliated or low-taxed. The two measures therefore target different forms of tax planning. Specifically, the 2014 provision focuses on payments to low-tax affiliates, whereas the 2021 rule limits excessive leverage more broadly.

2.2 Private Country-by-Country Reporting

As part of Action Item 13 of the OECD’s BEPS initiative, private CbCR is designed to increase tax transparency toward tax authorities by requiring large MNEs to report revenues, profits, employees, assets, and taxes paid on a jurisdiction-by-jurisdiction basis (De Simone and Olbert, 2022). The reporting framework requires in-scope MNEs to prepare a Master File, a Local File, and a Country-by-Country report. These reports are filed non-publicly with the tax authority in the parent company’s jurisdiction, which subsequently exchanges the information with tax authorities in jurisdictions in which the MNE operates.

Austria implemented these requirements through the *Verrechnungspreisdokumentationsgesetz* (VPDG; i.e., transfer pricing documentation law), effective for tax years beginning on or after January 1, 2016.⁴ The reporting obligation applies to MNEs with consolidated annual revenues exceeding EUR 750 million in the preceding fiscal year. Extractive industries and financial institutions are exempt because they were already subject to public CbCR under the 2013 Accounting Directive (Directive 2013/34/EU) and the 2013 Transparency Directive (Directive 2013/36/EU), respectively.⁵

The primary objective of private CbCR is to provide tax authorities with a clearer picture of an MNE’s global economic footprint and to facilitate more targeted tax audits, particularly of structures involving low-tax jurisdictions with disproportionately high profits but limited economic activity. Importantly, reports are shared only among tax authorities and are not publicly disclosed. If private CbCR increases the expected detection and enforcement risk associated with income shifting, exposed Austrian MNE entities should report higher taxable income following its implementation. At the same

⁴Austria had already established transfer pricing regulations prior to our sample period. In particular, the *Verrechnungspreisrichtlinien* 2010 (Transfer Pricing Guidelines 2010), based on the OECD Transfer Pricing Guidelines, codified principles previously developed through administrative practice and court cases.

⁵Mandatory public disclosure of CbC reports in the EU became effective for financial years beginning after June 21, 2024. Consequently, Austrian-headquartered MNEs will first publish public CbCR reports for fiscal years starting on or after January 1, 2025.

time, exposed MNEs might have incentives to increase economic activity in low-tax jurisdictions in order to substantiate their income-shifting activities and to reduce enforcement risk (De Simone and Olbert, 2022).

2.3 CFC Rule

Austria implemented Articles 7 and 8 of the ATAD through the *Annual Tax Act 2018*, introducing a CFC regime effective for tax years beginning on or after January 1, 2019. The rule targets foreign low-tax affiliates controlled by Austrian corporate shareholders. A foreign entity qualifies as a CFC if the Austrian parent directly or indirectly owns more than 50% of its shares.

Austria adopted a categorical approach under which only certain passive income, including interest, royalties, dividends, or finance lease income, is subject to inclusion at the Austrian parent level. Qualifying passive income is included proportionally to the parent's ownership share in the year it is earned by the subsidiary, regardless of whether profits are distributed. The rule applies if passive income is taxed below an effective rate of 12.5%.⁶ To avoid double taxation, subsequent dividend distributions corresponding to previously included CFC income are exempt from taxation in Austria.

By taxing low-taxed passive income at the parent level, the CFC rule reduces the benefits of shifting income abroad and subsequently repatriating such income through tax-exempt dividends (Markle, 2016). Accordingly, if the policy effectively constrains income shifting, exposed Austrian MNE entities should report higher taxable income following its implementation.

Yet, two important carve-outs limit the scope of the CFC regime. First, the rule does not apply if passive income accounts for less than one-third of the subsidiary's

⁶For tax years beginning on or after January 1, 2026, the low-tax threshold increases to 15%; following the global minimum tax rate under the OECD Pillar Two framework.

total income (i.e., more than two-thirds of the income result from active business activities). Second, subsidiaries with sufficient economic substance in the form of employees, assets, and business premises are exempt. These carve-outs create incentives for firms to increase economic activity or earn higher active income in low-tax jurisdictions in order to preserve the tax benefits of shifting income out of Austria.

Figure 1 illustrates the staggered implementation of the three anti-BEPS measures during our sample period. We expect each measure to alter the cost-benefit trade-off associated with cross-border income shifting and therefore to affect the equilibrium level of shifted income. The Austrian setting is particularly well-suited because the statutory corporate income tax rate remained constant at 25% throughout our sample period. This institutional feature allows us to compare the effects of the three anti-BEPS measures within a common tax environment while holding other tax incentives constant. As a result, we can isolate the effects of policy design from broader changes in tax incentives, particularly those arising from changes in domestic corporate tax rates. The staggered timing and distinct scope of the three measures also allow us to define distinct estimation windows and to construct clean treatment and control groups, providing a unique opportunity to compare how different anti-BEPS measures affect MNEs' income-shifting behavior and to what extent they induce alternative responses.

Figure 1: Timeline of the Adoption of Anti-BEPS Measures in Austria

3 Prior Literature

Much of the literature on anti-BEPS measures examines individual measures in isolation and provides mixed evidence regarding their effectiveness in constraining income shifting. At the same time, a growing body of research identifies alternative responses, such as substituting across shifting channels or reallocating economic activity. Because prior studies rarely analyze these responses jointly, existing evidence provides a limited picture of the overall effects of anti-BEPS policies. In the following, we summarize the existing evidence and highlight the open questions that motivate our analysis.

3.1 Interest and Royalty Deduction Limitation

Empirical evidence on the effects of measures targeting intra-group interest and royalty payments is limited. For the Austrian deduction limitation, Petutschnig (2018) documents a significant decline in the debt ratio of exposed entities, consistent with reduced incentives for intra-group debt financing. However, whether the rule constrains overall income shifting remains unclear.

Most prior work in non-Austrian settings focuses on thin capitalization rules and earnings stripping rules. These measures are conceptually related but narrower in scope because they target interest deductions only rather than both interest and royalty payments to low-tax affiliates.⁷ Consistent with these policies reducing the attractiveness of debt financing, Buettner et al. (2016) show that internal debt levels no longer respond to tax incentives once thin capitalization rules are in place. Similarly, Buslei and Simmler (2012) and Alberternst and Sureth (2015) document declines in debt ratios following the introduction of the German earnings-stripping rule in 2008.

⁷While thin capitalization rules limit the deductibility of interest payments based on a firm's debt-to-equity ratio, earnings stripping rules cap deductible net interest payments at a specific percentage of profits.

Beyond financing responses, some evidence suggests that MNEs substitute toward alternative shifting channels when debt shifting becomes less beneficial. In a cross-country setting, Saunders-Scott (2015) finds that entities exposed to earnings-stripping rules report lower earnings before interest and taxes (EBIT) after implementation. Because lower EBIT indicates greater use of transfer pricing and royalty-based shifting, these findings suggest substitution from debt shifting into other channels. However, it remains unclear whether similar substitution occurs under a measure that simultaneously targets both interest and royalty payments, as is the case in Austria.

3.2 Private Country-by-Country Reporting

The literature on private CbCR examines MNE responses along two dimensions. First, several studies evaluate the effectiveness of private CbCR in reducing income shifting and report mixed findings. Joshi (2020) exploits the introduction of private CbCR in the EU and finds no significant reduction in income shifting in the short run. Using a longer sample period and a broader sample, Adams (2024) documents a significant decrease in income shifting. In contrast, using U.S. administrative tax data, Nessa et al. (2025) find that U.S. MNEs subject to private CbCR neither reduce income shifting nor reallocate real activity. Doeleman et al. (2024) argue that these mixed findings might partly reflect a substitution away from shifting income out of medium-tax countries into tax havens toward shifting income out of high-tax countries.

Second, another stream of research examines MNEs' real responses to private CbCR. De Simone and Olbert (2022) find that MNE affiliates located in countries with preferential tax systems increase both capital and labor investment following exposure to private CbCR. Their findings suggest that firms respond to heightened transparency by increasing economic activity in low-tax jurisdictions, thereby strengthening the justification for profits reported in those locations. Focusing on regulatory avoidance, Hugger (2025) documents bunching just below the EUR 750 million revenue threshold

after the introduction of private CbCR, consistent with MNEs adjusting consolidated revenues to avoid the reporting requirement altogether.

While prior studies document both income shifting and real economic responses to private CbCR, these adjustments are typically studied in isolation. As a result, it remains unclear whether changes in economic activity directly facilitate income shifting. Further, prior research has not examined how the incentives created by private CbCR interact with other anti-BEPS measures and their efforts to constrain income shifting.

3.3 CFC Rule

The literature on CFC rules similarly examines both income-shifting responses (Prettl, 2017; Clifford, 2019; Schenkelberg, 2020) and real economic adjustments (Ruf and Weichenrieder, 2012; Clifford, 2019; Prettl and von Hagen, 2023; Gschossmann and Pfrang, 2024; Rechbauer et al., 2026). With respect to income shifting, Clifford (2019) analyzes an international sample of MNEs and finds that CFC rules reduce profits reported in subsidiaries subject to the regime, while increasing profits reported in subsidiaries just above the relevant low-tax threshold. Similarly, Schenkelberg (2020) documents higher profits in low-tax subsidiaries not targeted by CFC rules, particularly among MNEs with stronger shifting incentives and greater opportunities. Combined, these findings suggest that although CFC rules can constrain income shifting to low-tax jurisdictions, MNEs strategically exploit tax-rate thresholds and reallocate profits toward entities that remain outside the scope of the regime.

A separate stream of research examines real responses to CFC rules. Prettl and von Hagen (2023) show that MNEs are less likely to acquire targets whose income would subsequently fall under CFC taxation while Clifford (2019) finds that MNEs incorporate fewer new entities in jurisdictions below the low-tax threshold. Studying reforms to the German CFC regime, Ruf and Weichenrieder (2013) document increased investments in low-tax subsidiaries not affected by the rules. Focusing on ATAD-based

CFC reforms in Europe, Rechbauer et al. (2026) find an overall decline in the share of subsidiaries located in low-tax jurisdictions, although this effect vanishes for regimes with an economic substance exemption. Using the same setting, Gschossmann and Pfrang (2024) document increases in economic activity in low-taxed subsidiaries while their financial income remains largely unchanged.

While prior research suggests that CFC rules affect both income shifting and real economic activity, it has paid limited attention to the role of active-income safe harbors in shaping these responses. It therefore remains unclear whether MNEs strategically change active business activity in low-tax jurisdictions to preserve income shifting.

Taken together, our study extends the existing literature in several ways. First, rather than examining anti-BEPS measures in isolation, we analyze multiple measures and their potential interactions within a single institutional environment. Second, we jointly examine income-shifting responses and other adjustments, allowing us to directly link potential changes in income shifting to underlying changes in economic activity. Third, to the best of our knowledge, we are the first to provide evidence on a policy targeting both intra-group interest and royalty payments as well as on the role of active-income safe harbors in shaping MNEs' response to CFC rules.

4 Data, Sample, and Research Design

4.1 Data Sources

We construct the dataset for our analysis by combining four complementary data sources. First, we obtain administrative corporate tax return data from the Austria Micro Data Center (AMDC), which provides access to tax return data collected by the Austrian Ministry of Finance. Second, we use unconsolidated financial statement data from Bureau van Dijk's Orbis Historical Database, including pre-tax profit, total assets, fixed assets, costs of employees, and interest expenses. Third, we supplement these

data with unconsolidated financial statement data from Bureau van Dijk’s SABINA database, which provides more detailed financial statement information for Austrian firms subject to mandatory disclosure requirements than regular Orbis.⁸ Fourth, we obtain data on corporate ownership structures from inward and outward foreign affiliate statistics (IFATS and OFATS), which are also available through the AMDC. IFATS identify Austrian entities owned by foreign shareholders, whereas OFATS identify foreign subsidiaries owned by Austrian firms. These data allow us to reconstruct group structures and assign statutory corporate income tax rates to foreign affiliates.

To ensure taxpayer confidentiality, the AMDC merges the tax return data with the financial statement data using entities’ trade register numbers before providing access to the data. The resulting dataset is fully pseudonymized and contains no identifying taxpayer information. Our final sample covers the period from 2011 to 2019.

4.2 Sample Selection

To construct the samples used in our analyses, we begin with a panel of Austrian MNE entities spanning the years 2011 to 2019.⁹ The dataset includes all entity-year observations for which the AMDC successfully merged administrative tax return data with financial statement information. We classify an Austrian entity as multinational if it either owns more than 50% of a foreign entity’s equity or if a foreign shareholder owns more than 50% of the entity’s equity. We restrict the sample to entities incorporated under the Austrian commercial code (*Unternehmensgesetzbuch*) and retain only public and private limited corporations (*AG* and *GmbH*). In addition, we exclude firms filing consolidated tax returns under the Austrian group taxation regime because these firms face different income-shifting incentives (Rünger, 2019).

⁸These firms primarily include corporations, such as public and private limited companies, as well as partnerships without personally liable shareholders, most notably *GmbH & Co KG* structures.

⁹We begin in 2011 because, due to a change in the reporting standard, OFATS and IFATS data from earlier years are not comparable. We end in 2019 as the last year with available tax return data.

For each anti-BEPS measure, we construct a separate time-specific subsample using a consistent sample selection procedure. Specifically, each subsample is based on a six-year event window centered around the implementation of the respective policy, consisting of three years before and three years after implementation. Because our data end in 2019, the analysis of the CFC rule includes only one post-reform year. We further restrict each subsample to entities that can be assigned to either the treatment or control group. Finally, we exclude observations with missing taxable income data or missing information required to compute control variables.

Table 1 summarizes the sample selection procedure for each analysis. Panel A reports the final sample for the interest and royalty deduction limitation (Sample 1), which consists of 2,980 entity-year observations covering 739 unique entities over the period 2011–2016. Panel B reports the sample used to analyze private CbCR (Sample 2), which contains 3,724 entity-year observations from 935 entities over the period 2013–2018. Panel C presents the sample for the CFC rule analysis (Sample 3), which comprises 2,536 entity-year observations representing 848 firms over the period 2016–2019. Samples used to analyze alternative adjustment responses may be smaller due to differences in data availability across outcome variables.

Table 1: Sample Selection

Panel A: Sample 1 – Interest and Royalty Deduction Limitation		
Selection Step	# Observations	# Entities
MNE Entity-year observations (2011–2016)	60,336	12,879
Less: Not part of treatment or control group	-35,486	
Less: Missing taxable income	-7,850	
Less: Missing fixed assets	-2,300	
Less: Missing cost of employees	-11,720	
Final Sample	2,980	739
Panel B: Sample 2 – Private CbCR		
Selection Step	# Observations	# Entities
MNE Entity-year observations (2013–2018)	63,273	13,571
Less: Financial and extractive industries	-2,538	
Less: Not part of treatment or control group	-27,920	
Less: Missing taxable income	-10,788	
Less: Missing fixed assets	-2,929	
Less: Missing cost of employees	-15,374	
Final Sample	3,724	935
Panel C: Sample 3 – CFC Rule		
Selection Step	# Observations	# Entities
MNE Entity-year observations (2016–2019)	42,839	12,320
Less: Not part of treatment or control group	-22,727	
Less: Missing taxable income	-6,377	
Less: Missing fixed assets	-1,995	
Less: Missing cost of employees	-9,204	
Final Sample	2,536	848

Note: This table presents the sample selection for our analyses of the three anti-BEPS measures: (i) the interest and royalty deduction limitation in Panel A, (ii) private CbCR in Panel B, and (iii) the CFC rule in Panel C.

4.3 Research Design

In our baseline analysis, we examine the impact of each anti-BEPS measure on the income-shifting behavior of potentially affected Austrian MNE entities. To do so, we draw on the income-shifting framework of Hines and Rice (1994) and implement a difference-in-differences specification. Specifically, we estimate the change in the taxable income reported by exposed Austrian MNE entities in response to the introduction of a given anti-BEPS measure relative to unaffected entities, while controlling for production inputs:

$$\begin{aligned} \ln(\text{TaxableIncome})_{i,t} = & \beta_0 + \gamma \times \text{Treat}_i \times \text{Post}_t + \beta_1 \times \ln(\text{FixedAssets})_{i,t} \\ & + \beta_2 \times \ln(\text{CostsEmployees})_{i,t} + \text{EntityFE}_i + \text{TimeFE}_t + \epsilon_{i,t}. \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Our dependent variable, $\ln(\text{TaxableIncome})$, is the natural logarithm of taxable income reported by Austrian MNE entity i in year t . The key variable of interest is the interaction term between the treatment indicator Treat and the post-reform indicator Post . For each policy, we construct distinct treatment groups based on an entity's ex-ante exposure to the respective measure. Because we define treatment status based on exposure prior to implementation rather than based on realized responses, our approach closely resembles an intention-to-treat design.

Our primary measure for determining treatment status is the tax-rate differential between the Austrian statutory corporate income tax rate and the lowest-taxed foreign affiliate within the MNE group (TRD).¹⁰ During our sample period, the Austrian statutory corporate income tax rate remained constant at 25%. Accordingly, the tax-rate differential for a given Austrian MNE entity is given by:

$$\text{TRD} = \tau_{\text{Austria}} - \tau_{\text{Foreign}} = 25 - \tau_{\text{Foreign}}.$$

¹⁰We collect statutory corporate income tax rate data from the Tax Foundation.

We classify an entity as treated if TRD exceeds the relevant low-tax threshold for a given anti-BEPS measure x . More formally, $Treat$ is determined as follows:

$$Treat = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } TRD > x, \\ 0 & \text{if } TRD < 0. \end{cases}$$

For the interest and royalty deduction limitation, we classify Austrian MNE entities as treated if their tax-rate differential exceeds 15 percentage points in the year prior to implementation. This threshold reflects that the rule applies if payments are taxed below 10% at the recipient level, i.e., if $TRD > 15$. For the CFC rule, we classify entities as treated if the tax-rate differential exceeds 12.5 percentage points in 2018, the year prior to implementation. This threshold again corresponds to the low-tax threshold for the Austrian CFC regime.

Because the applicability of private CbCR does not depend on a comparable low-tax threshold, but rather on group-level sales revenue which we do not observe in our data, we define treatment status differently for this policy. Specifically, we classify Austrian MNE entities as treated if their lowest-taxed foreign affiliate is located in a tax haven in 2015. This approach is consistent with the idea that private CbCR increases transparency regarding global operations, particularly those in tax havens.¹¹

A key advantage of our approach is the relatively clean identification of treatment status using administrative foreign affiliate statistics (FATS). Compared with commercial databases such as Orbis, administrative FATS data provide substantially broader coverage of low-tax affiliates (Bajgar et al., 2020), which are the primary targets of

¹¹We classify tax haven affiliates using the list by Hines (2010).

anti-BEPS measures.¹² As a result, our setting likely captures exposure to anti-BEPS measures more comprehensively than prior studies without administrative data.

By construction, treated entities for all three anti-BEPS measures have incentives to shift income out of Austria because their lowest-taxed foreign affiliate faces a tax rate below the Austrian rate. As a control group, we use Austrian MNE entities with inward-shifting incentives, i.e., entities that belong to an MNE whose lowest-taxed foreign affiliate is located in a country with a statutory corporate income tax rate above the Austrian rate ($TRD < 0$). Because the implementation of anti-BEPS measures in Austria does not alter the incentives to shift income into Austria, these entities should not be affected by the policies. We exclude observations with a tax-rate differential of zero because these entities face no incentives to shift income across borders.

Post is a post-reform indicator equal to one for years after the respective anti-BEPS measure became effective, and zero otherwise. For the interest and royalty deduction limitation, *Post* equals one for years from 2014 onward. For private CbCR, *Post* equals one for years from 2016 onward. For the CFC rule, *Post* equals one in 2019.

For each policy, we run separate regressions with the respective definition of *Treat* and *Post*. The coefficient on the interaction term $Treat \times Post$ represents our difference-in-differences estimator and captures the change in taxable income of Austrian MNE entities exposed to a given anti-BEPS measure (first difference) relative to counterfactual entities that are not exposed (second difference). Table 2 summarizes the definitions of *Treat* and *Post* for each anti-BEPS measure.

We control for entity-level production inputs in the form of capital and labor by including the natural logarithm of fixed assets and the cost of employees. Including

¹²As noted by Amberger et al. (2026), one limitation of the FATS data is that they do not capture “sister entities” that are owned by a foreign MNE affiliate but that have no ownership ties to the Austrian entity. Consequently, some Austrian MNE entities may be misclassified as untreated if a lower-taxed foreign sister affiliate exists outside the observed ownership chain. To the extent that such misclassification occurs, it should attenuate our estimated treatment effects and bias against finding results. Our estimates therefore likely represent a lower bound of MNEs’ responses to anti-BEPS measures.

Table 2: Definition of *Treat* and *Post* for each anti-BEPS measure

Anti-BEPS Measure	<i>Treat</i> = 1 if	<i>Post</i> = 1 if
Interest and Royalty Deduction Limitation	$TRD > 15$ in 2013	$t \geq 2014$
Private CbCR	Tax Haven Presence in 2015	$t \geq 2016$
CFC Rule	$TRD > 12.5$ in 2018	$t = 2019$

Note: This table summarizes the definition of *Treat* and *Post* for each anti-BEPS measure.

these variables allows us to account for the level of “normal” income generated through the use of productive inputs. We further include entity fixed effects to absorb time-invariant entity characteristics and year fixed effects to control for macroeconomic shocks and common time trends. Given this fixed-effects structure, the coefficients on *Treat* and *Post* are absorbed by the estimation, such that identification is based on within-entity changes in exposure to a given anti-BEPS measure. Following Petersen (2009), we cluster standard errors at the entity level.

4.4 Descriptive Statistics

Table 3 presents descriptive statistics for each regression sample. Panel A reports statistics for Sample 1 (the interest and royalty deduction limitation), Panel B for Sample 2 (private CbCR), and Panel C for Sample 3 (CFC rule). For each sample, we report descriptive statistics for both the raw variables and their logged transformations used in the multivariate analysis.

In Panel A, 1% of the observations belong to the treatment group, suggesting that relatively few Austrian MNE entities have affiliates located in jurisdictions with statutory corporate tax rates below 10%. On average, entities in this sample report annual taxable income of EUR 3.5 million, hold fixed assets of EUR 46.5 million, and incur employee expenses of EUR 8.3 million. In Panel B, 17% of the observations are classified as treated. Relative to Panel A, entities in this sample exhibit somewhat higher taxable income and employee expenses, while average fixed assets are lower. In

Panel C, 7% of the observations belong to the treatment group. Average fixed assets amount to EUR 30.8 million, which is comparable to the levels reported in Panel B.

Overall, the descriptive statistics suggest that the samples used across all three analyses are broadly comparable in terms of taxable income and labor input, while differing somewhat with respect to firm size and the share of treated entities.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics

Panel A: Sample 1 - Interest and Royalty Deduction Limitation			
Variable	Obs.	Mean	SD
Treat	2,980	0.01	0.12
Post	2,980	0.51	0.50
Fixed Assets	2,980	46,464,079.03	741,334,880.46
Costs of Employees	2,980	8,335,296.44	14,046,821.38
Taxable Income	2,980	3,469,892.77	13,840,867.38
Interest	2,980	532,637.01	8,026,599.27
Debt	2,980	18,649,282.28	112,773,439.05
Royalty Payments	2,980	3,089,621.92	23,187,520.88
EBIT	2,980	7,092,151.70	29,958,373.23
ln(Fixed Assets)	2,980	14.51	2.15
ln(Costs of Employees)	2,980	15.21	1.28
ln(Taxable Income)	2,980	13.91	1.32
ln(Interest)	2,391	9.72	3.05
ln(Debt)	2,774	15.32	1.43
ln(Royalty Payments)	867	15.15	1.22
ln(EBIT)	2,980	14.57	1.44

Panel B: Sample 2 - Private CbCR

Variable	Obs.	Mean	SD
Treat	3,724	0.17	0.37
Post	3,724	0.53	0.50
Fixed Assets	3,724	29,934,758.84	468,495,702.43
Costs of Employees	3,724	9,008,155.20	15,150,390.75
Taxable Income	3,724	3,897,640.14	13,999,800.61
Interest	3,724	626,828.23	10,559,283.14
Debt	3,723	15,541,010.70	96,059,064.83
Royalty Payments	3,724	6,007,109.77	26,933,416.25
EBIT	3,724	10,531,578.12	34,957,490.91
ln(Fixed Assets)	3,724	14.55	2.16
ln(Costs of Employees)	3,724	15.29	1.25
ln(Taxable Income)	3,724	13.91	1.31
ln(Interest)	2,982	9.77	3.06
ln(Debt)	2,979	15.12	1.66
ln(Royalty Payments)	2,342	15.14	1.23
ln(EBIT)	3,724	15.03	1.36
ln(Total Employees)	173	3.57	1.60
ln(Total Sales)	177	9.15	1.75

Panel C: Sample 3 - CFC Rule

Variable	Obs.	Mean	SD
Treat	2,536	0.07	0.26
Post	2,536	0.26	0.44
Fixed Assets	2,536	30,872,232.91	348,800,366.21
Costs of Employees	2,536	9,210,678.56	19,685,507.98
Taxable Income	2,536	4,341,556.69	12,251,730.13
Interest	2,536	1,030,428.53	15,315,133.77
Debt	2,534	13,941,412.07	113,447,314.38
Royalty Payments	2,536	9,188,979.17	31,887,349.81
EBIT	2,536	14,560,964.39	41,764,016.85
ln(Fixed Assets)	2,536	14.53	2.35
ln(Costs of Employees)	2,536	15.26	1.29
ln(Taxable Income)	2,536	13.95	1.33
ln(Interest)	1,993	9.78	2.96
ln(Debt)	1,650	14.71	1.93
ln(Royalty Payments)	2,444	15.10	1.29
ln(EBIT)	2,536	15.50	1.12
ln(Total Employees)	185	3.76	1.74
ln(Total Sales)	195	9.38	1.88

Note: This table presents descriptive statistics for each sample used in our multivariate analysis. Panel A reports statistics for Sample 1 (interest and royalty deduction limitation), Panel B for Sample 2 (private CbCR), and Panel C for Sample 3 (CFC rule). For each sample, we report the number of observations, the mean, and the standard deviation for each variable. We report descriptive statistics for both the raw variables and their logged transformations used in the multivariate analysis. We provide detailed variable descriptions in the Appendix.

5 Regression Results

5.1 Interest and Royalty Deduction Limitation

Income-Shifting Response

We begin our multivariate analysis by examining MNEs' income-shifting response to the interest and royalty deduction limitation introduced in 2014. Panel A of Table 4 reports the results of estimating equation (1). Column (1) includes entity and year fixed effects, but no controls. The remaining specifications include control variables while varying the fixed-effects structure. Specifically, columns (2) and (4) include entity and year fixed effects, whereas columns (3) and (5) include industry and year fixed effects. In columns (4) and (5), we further apply kernel-based propensity score matching and match treated and control firms based on pre-reform firm characteristics, namely fixed assets and the cost of employees. This approach should improve the comparability between treated and control entities and mitigate concerns that observable differences between the two groups drive our results.

Across all specifications, the coefficient on $Treat \times Post$ ($p < 0.05$) is positive and statistically significant, indicating that exposed Austrian MNE entities report higher taxable income following the introduction of the deduction limitation. Economically, the estimate in column (4) implies that treated entities increase taxable income by 133% relative to the control group.¹³ At the sample mean, this estimate corresponds to an increase in taxable income of approximately EUR 4.6 million per entity-year. These findings suggest that limiting the deductibility of intra-group interest and royalty payments to low-tax foreign affiliates constrains income shifting out of Austria.

Panel B of Table 4 presents a placebo analysis in which we modify the treatment definition. Instead of classifying entities with a tax-rate differential (TRD) above 15 as treated, we define a pseudo-treatment group with entities whose TRD is between 0

¹³We calculate this effect as follows: $e^{0.8448} - 1 = 1.3275$.

and 15 in 2013. Like our initial treatment group, these entities have incentives to shift income out of Austria, but they are not exposed to the deduction limitation because their lowest-taxed foreign affiliate faces a statutory corporate income tax rate between 10% and 25%.¹⁴ Consistent with this institutional feature, the coefficient on $Treat \times Post$ is statistically insignificant and economically small across all specifications. The absence of a significant change in taxable income for this pseudo-treatment group alleviates concerns that our main findings merely capture differences between entities with inward- and outward-shifting incentives rather than the effect of the policy itself.

The key identifying assumption underlying our difference-in-differences design is that treated and control entities would have exhibited similar trends in taxable income absent the reform (Roberts and Whited, 2013). Although this parallel-trends assumption is inherently untestable, we provide supporting evidence using an event-study framework and estimate annual treatment effects. Specifically, we modify equation (1) by interacting $Treat$ with separate year indicators. The resulting interaction terms capture yearly differences in taxable income between treated and control entities relative to the omitted base year 2013.

Figure 2 plots the estimated treatment effects together with their 90% confidence interval. The pre-treatment estimates for 2011 and 2012 are statistically insignificant and economically close to zero, providing support for the validity of the parallel-trends assumption (Roberts and Whited, 2013). Following the introduction of the deduction limitation in 2014, we observe a sharp and statistically significant relative increase in taxable income among treatment entities ($p < 0.05$). In 2015, the estimated effect increases further and remains at a similar level in 2016. Overall, these findings suggest that the deduction limitation affected the income-shifting behavior of exposed MNE entities immediately upon implementation and that its effects strengthened over time.

¹⁴For example, if the lowest foreign tax rate within the group equals 13%, then $TRD = 25 - \tau_{Foreign} = 25 - 13 = 12$, implying that the deduction limitation does not apply.

Table 4: Interest and Royalty Deduction Limitation - Income-Shifting Response

Panel A: Baseline Analysis					
	ln(Taxable Income)				
	No Controls	Unmatched		Matched	
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
Treat \times Post	0.8046** (0.3844)	0.8504** (0.3695)	1.0824** (0.4290)	0.8448** (0.3704)	0.8738** (0.3507)
Treat			-0.6881 (0.5065)		-0.7979* (0.4786)
ln(Fixed Assets)		-0.0336 (0.0308)	0.1250*** (0.0215)	0.0481 (0.0540)	0.2356*** (0.0558)
ln(Costs of Employees)		0.3929*** (0.0966)	0.3821*** (0.0398)	0.4569** (0.2073)	0.3699*** (0.0724)
Entity FE	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Industry FE	No	No	Yes	No	Yes
No. singletons	110	110	-	31	-
Obs.	2,870	2,870	2,980	2,708	2,739
R^2	0.78	0.79	0.24	0.75	0.33
Panel B: Placebo Analysis					
	ln(Taxable Income)				
	No Controls	Unmatched		Matched	
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
Treat \times Post	0.0467 (0.0632)	0.0664 (0.0622)	0.0991 (0.0733)	0.0705 (0.0627)	0.1101 (0.0693)
Treat			-0.2561*** (0.0819)		-0.2334*** (0.0809)
ln(Fixed Assets)		-0.0504* (0.0267)	0.1094*** (0.0176)	-0.0508* (0.0275)	0.1065*** (0.0200)
ln(Costs of Employees)		0.3645*** (0.0780)	0.3976*** (0.0324)	0.3548*** (0.0846)	0.3808*** (0.0357)
Entity FE	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Industry FE	No	No	Yes	No	Yes
No. singletons	180	180	-	64	-
Obs.	4,094	4,094	4,274	3,860	3,924
R^2	0.79	0.79	0.26	0.77	0.26

Note: This table presents the results of the analysis of MNEs' income-shifting responses to the 2014 introduction of the interest and royalty deduction limitation. We perform the baseline analysis in Panel A and a placebo analysis in Panel B. In both panels, we use the natural logarithm of taxable income as the dependent variable. In column (1), we include no control variables. We use an unmatched sample in columns (2) and (3), and a matched sample in columns (4) and (5). We apply kernel-based propensity score matching based on pre-reform characteristics. In columns (1), (2), and (4), we include entity and year fixed effects. In columns (3) and (5), we include industry and year fixed effects. We provide detailed variable descriptions in the Appendix. We cluster standard errors by entity. ***, **, and * indicate significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10 % levels.

Figure 2: Interest and Royalty Deduction Limitation - Event Study Estimates for Income-Shifting Response

Note: This figure plots the annual treatment effects for MNEs' income-shifting response to the interest and royalty deduction limitation together with their 90% confidence interval. The dependent variable is the natural logarithm of taxable income. We interact *Treat* with separate year indicators to obtain annual treatment estimates. These treatment effects capture the difference in taxable income between entities in the treatment group and the control group relative to the year before the introduction of the interest and royalty deduction limitation (i.e., 2013).

Additional Responses: Substitution across Income-Shifting Channels

The results from our income-shifting analysis suggest a substantial increase in reported taxable income among exposed Austrian MNE entities following the introduction of the interest and royalty deduction limitation, which is consistent with a reduction in outward income shifting. However, because changes in taxable income capture the net change in income shifting, the observed increase in taxable income could mask offsetting responses along different income-shifting channels. In particular, MNEs might respond to the reduced attractiveness of intra-group interest and royalty payments by substituting toward other strategies, such as transfer-pricing manipulation.

To examine this possibility, we modify equation (1) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \ln(Outcome)_{i,t} = & \beta_0 + \gamma \times Treat_i \times Post_t + \beta_1 \times \ln(FixedAssets)_{i,t} \\ & + \beta_2 \times \ln(CostsEmployees)_{i,t} + EntityFE_i + TimeFE_t + \epsilon_{i,t}. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Relative to equation (1), the specification differs with respect to the dependent variable. Specifically, we use a set of alternative outcome variables designed to capture potential adjustments in three major income-shifting channels available to MNEs: (i) transfer-pricing manipulation for the intra-group sale of goods and services, (ii) intra-group debt financing, and (iii) royalty-based income shifting.

To isolate changes in transfer pricing, we construct a modified measure of earnings before interest and taxes (*EBIT*) for the Austrian MNE entities in our sample, defined as taxable income net of interest expenses and royalty payments. By excluding interest and royalty payments, this measure captures variation in profitability that is primarily attributable to transfer pricing (e.g., Heckemeyer and Overesch, 2017). To examine potential adjustments in debt shifting, we use both the natural logarithm of long-term debt (*Debt*) and the natural logarithm of interest expenses (*Interest*).¹⁵ Finally, to capture potential changes in royalty-based shifting, we use the natural logarithm of other business expenses as a proxy for royalty payments. We provide detailed variable descriptions in the Appendix.

Table 5 reports the estimation results. Panel A presents estimates based on the unmatched sample, whereas Panel B reports estimates after applying kernel-based propensity score matching. Across both panels, the coefficients on $Treat \times Post$ are statistically insignificant.¹⁶ These findings indicate that exposed MNE entities do not offset the reduced attractiveness of intra-group interest and royalty payments by increasing the use of alternative income-shifting channels. For example, if treated Austrian MNE entities responded by intensifying transfer-pricing manipulation, such as by increasing transfer prices for intra-group goods and services provided to the Austrian MNE entity, we would expect a decline in the modified *EBIT* measure. Higher transfer prices

¹⁵Given that we rely on financial statement data to construct proxies for debt shifting, we cannot distinguish between external and internal debt. To the extent that interest expenses or long-term debt reflect external financing, we measure debt shifting with noise.

¹⁶Due to the limited availability of information on royalty payments in our sample, the coefficient on $Treat \times Post$ is collinear with the fixed effects in column (4) and therefore absorbed in the estimation.

would raise deductible input costs in Austria, lower reported EBIT, and thereby shift additional income abroad. However, we find no evidence consistent with such behavior.

Overall, our findings provide no evidence for MNEs substituting toward alternative income-shifting channels in response to the deduction limitation. This result is consistent with the notion that transfer-pricing arrangements for goods and services are less flexible and more costly to adjust than royalty- or debt-based shifting strategies (Hoplund et al., 2018). Hence, in contrast to policies only targeting debt shifting, where prior research finds substitution (Saunders-Scott, 2015), anti-BEPS measures that simultaneously target intra-group interest and royalty payments appear to constrain cross-border income shifting without inducing substitution.

Table 5: Interest and Royalty Deduction Limitation - Income-Shifting Channels

Panel A: Unmatched Sample				
	$\ln(\text{EBIT})$	$\ln(\text{Interest})$	$\ln(\text{Debt})$	$\ln(\text{Royalty Payments})$
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
Treat \times Post	0.3017 (0.3747)	-0.4460 (1.0553)	0.0466 (0.2229)	
$\ln(\text{Fixed Assets})$	-0.0660** (0.0294)	0.3172*** (0.1029)	0.1966*** (0.0380)	-0.0169 (0.0329)
$\ln(\text{Costs of Employees})$	0.3858*** (0.0779)	0.1106 (0.1782)	0.3058*** (0.1047)	0.2690* (0.1387)
Entity FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
No. singletons	110	39	16	229
Obs.	2,870	2,264	2,110	278
R^2	0.81	0.81	0.88	0.97

Panel B: Matched Sample				
	ln(EBIT)	ln(Interest)	ln(Debt)	ln(Royalty Payments)
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
Treat \times Post	0.3470 (0.3743)	-0.5765 (1.0546)	0.0688 (0.2067)	
ln(Fixed Assets)	0.0385 (0.0360)	0.1893 (0.1383)	0.1981*** (0.0487)	0.0454 (0.1187)
ln(Costs of Employees)	0.4841** (0.2177)	-0.4317 (0.6005)	0.2825** (0.1153)	0.6673 (0.4119)
Entity FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
No. singletons	31	31	10	219
Obs.	2,708	2,163	2,022	240
R^2	0.79	0.75	0.88	0.94

Note: This table presents the results of the analysis of alternative responses to the 2014 introduction of the interest and royalty deduction limitation, focusing on potential substitution across income-shifting channels. Column (1) uses the natural logarithm of modified EBIT as the dependent variable; columns (2) and (3) use the natural logarithms of interest expenses and long-term debt, respectively; and column (4) uses the natural logarithm of royalty payments. Panel A reports the results for the unmatched sample, and Panel B reports results for the matched sample. We apply kernel-based propensity score matching based on pre-reform characteristics. All specifications include entity and year fixed effects. We provide detailed variable descriptions in the Appendix. We cluster standard errors by entity. ***, **, and * indicate significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10 % levels.

5.2 Private Country-by-Country Reporting

5.2.1 Income-Shifting Response

We next examine MNEs' income-shifting response to the second anti-BEPS measure in our setting, namely the introduction of private CbCR in 2016. Table 6 reports the results.¹⁷ As in the previous analysis, column (1) reports estimates of equation (1) including entity and year fixed effects, but excluding control variables. Columns (2) and (3) present estimates based on the unmatched sample, whereas columns (4) and (5) report results after applying kernel-based propensity score matching.

Across all specifications, the coefficient on $Treat \times Post$ is negative but statistically insignificant. These findings suggest that the introduction of private CbCR did not sig-

¹⁷We do not perform a placebo analysis for this policy because private CbCR does not feature a low-tax threshold comparable to the interest and royalty deduction limitation. As a result, constructing a clearly defined placebo group is not feasible in this case.

nificantly alter income shifting among exposed Austrian MNE entities. The results are broadly consistent with prior evidence based on U.S. administrative tax data, which similarly finds limited income-shifting responses to private CbCR (Nessa et al., 2025). One caveat, however, is that our treatment definition is necessarily imperfect because we do not observe consolidated group revenue. Consequently, the treatment (control) group may include entities belonging to MNE groups with consolidated revenue below (above) the EUR 750 million threshold and therefore outside (within) the scope of private CbCR. To the extent that this feature introduces measurement error in treatment assignment, our estimates are likely biased toward finding insignificant effects.

To shed light on the evolution of income shifting around the adoption of the policy, we again estimate equation (1) within an event-study framework and visualize the results in Figure 3. Using 2015 as the base year, we find that taxable income among treated entities trends upward relative to the control group in the pre-reform period (i.e., between 2013 and 2015), although these estimates are statistically insignificant. This pattern provides support for the validity of the parallel trends assumption. Following the introduction of private CbCR, however, taxable income among treated entities declines relative to the control group. The treatment effect becomes statistically significant in 2017 ($p < 0.1$), suggesting that exposed Austrian MNE entities shift *more* income out of Austria in the years after the reform.

Table 6: Private CbCR - Income-Shifting Response

	ln(Taxable Income)				
	No Controls	Unmatched		Matched	
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
Treat \times Post	-0.0799 (0.0908)	-0.0713 (0.0878)	-0.1235 (0.1041)	-0.0796 (0.0875)	-0.1389 (0.1030)
Treat			-0.2281** (0.1014)		-0.1964* (0.1023)
ln(Fixed Assets)		-0.0468 (0.0290)	0.1100*** (0.0189)	-0.1203** (0.0493)	0.0799** (0.0316)
ln(Costs of Employees)		0.4299*** (0.0772)	0.3709*** (0.0355)	0.5482*** (0.0923)	0.3806*** (0.0553)
Entity FE	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Industry FE	No	No	Yes	No	Yes
No. singletons	155	155	-	32	-
Obs.	3,569	3,569	3,724	3,281	3,313
R^2	0.78	0.78	0.21	0.77	0.22

Note: This table presents the results of the analysis of MNEs' income-shifting responses to the 2016 introduction of private CbCR. We use the natural logarithm of taxable income as the dependent variable. In column (1), we include no control variables. We use an unmatched sample in columns (2) and (3), and a matched sample in columns (4) and (5). We apply kernel-based propensity score matching based on pre-reform characteristics. In columns (1), (2), and (4), we include entity and year fixed effects. In columns (3) and (5), we include industry and year fixed effects. We provide detailed variable descriptions in the Appendix. We cluster standard errors by entity. ***, **, and * indicate significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10 % levels.

Figure 3: Private CbCR - Event Study Estimates for Income-Shifting Response

Note: This figure plots the annual treatment effects for the income-shifting response to private CbCR together with their 90% confidence interval. The dependent variable is the natural logarithm of taxable income. We interact *Treat* with separate year indicators to obtain annual treatment estimates. These treatment effects capture the difference in taxable income between entities in the treatment group and the control group relative to the year before the introduction of private CbCR (i.e., 2015).

5.2.2 Additional Responses

Income-Shifting Channels

The analysis in the previous section suggests that private CbCR is associated with a moderate increase in income shifting in the years following its introduction. To test whether exposed MNE entities adjust specific income-shifting channels, we again estimate equation (2) and report the results in Table 7.

Across both the unmatched sample (Panel A) and the matched sample (Panel B), we find a statistically significant increase in long-term debt among treated entities relative to the control group following the introduction of private CbCR (column (3), $p < 0.05$). This finding suggests that exposed MNEs increase debt-based income shifting in response to the new reporting requirements, thereby contributing to the overall increase in income shifting observed in Table 6.¹⁸

Table 7: Private CbCR - Income-Shifting Channels

Panel A: Unmatched Sample				
	ln(EBIT)	ln(Interest)	ln(Debt)	ln(Royalty Payments)
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
Treat \times Post	-0.0142 (0.0881)	-0.1895 (0.1740)	0.2574** (0.1197)	-0.0276 (0.0486)
ln(Fixed Assets)	-0.0659** (0.0300)	0.3172*** (0.0839)	0.1962*** (0.0558)	0.0509*** (0.0186)
ln(Costs of Employees)	0.3777*** (0.0696)	-0.0741 (0.2646)	0.3824** (0.1603)	0.4891*** (0.0462)
Entity FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Industry FE	No	No	No	No
No. singletons	155	59	34	145
Obs.	3,569	2,802	2,254	1,091
R^2	0.83	0.81	0.76	0.98

¹⁸Importantly, the interest and royalty deduction limitation was partly in effect during the pre-treatment period of the private CbCR analysis. Consequently, the observed increase in debt financing after the introduction of private CbCR likely reflects intra-group lending arrangements involving affiliates located in jurisdictions where interest income is taxed above 10% and therefore not subject to the deduction limitation.

Panel B: Matched Sample

	ln(EBIT)	ln(Interest)	ln(Debt)	ln(Royalty Payments)
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
Treat \times Post	-0.0161 (0.0877)	-0.1720 (0.1721)	0.2860** (0.1213)	-0.0423 (0.0455)
ln(Fixed Assets)	-0.1415*** (0.0395)	0.3986*** (0.0980)	0.2822*** (0.0636)	0.0377 (0.0266)
ln(Costs of Employees)	0.5359*** (0.1247)	-0.3415* (0.1860)	0.1491 (0.2182)	0.5178*** (0.0608)
Entity FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Industry FE	No	No	No	No
No. singletons	32	44	24	138
Obs.	3,281	2,590	2,110	995
R^2	0.82	0.84	0.76	0.99

Note: This table presents the results of the analysis of alternative responses to the 2016 introduction of private CbCR, focusing on income-shifting channels. Column (1) uses the natural logarithm of modified EBIT as the dependent variable; columns (2) and (3) use the natural logarithms of interest expenses and long-term debt, respectively; and column (4) uses the natural logarithm of royalty payments. Panel A reports the results for the unmatched sample, and Panel B reports results for the matched sample. We apply kernel-based propensity score matching based on pre-reform characteristics. All specifications include entity and year fixed effects. We provide detailed variable descriptions in the Appendix. We cluster standard errors by entity. ***, **, and * indicate significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10 % levels.

Real Economic Responses

The observed increase in income shifting following the introduction of private CbCR raises the question of how exposed MNEs are able to sustain or even expand income shifting despite providing tax authorities with more granular information on their global operations. One potential explanation is that MNEs reallocate economic activity to low-tax jurisdictions in order to substantiate the profits reported in those affiliates and support continued income shifting (De Simone and Olbert, 2022). To test for this mechanism, we use affiliate-level data from the OFATS database, which contains data on sales and employment for foreign affiliates owned by Austrian entities. For each Austrian MNE entity in our sample, we aggregate sales and employment across affiliates located in the jurisdiction of the entity's lowest-taxed foreign affiliate. We then use the natural logarithm of these measures as dependent variables in equation (1), which we

estimate within an event-study framework.¹⁹

Figure 4 plots the resulting dynamic treatment effects. We find that employment in foreign low-tax affiliates of treated Austrian MNE entities increases following the introduction of private CbCR. The estimated treatment effects are insignificant in 2016 and 2017 and statistically significant at conventional levels two years after implementation, i.e., in 2018 ($p < 0.1$). In contrast, we find no statistically significant changes in sales reported by foreign low-tax affiliates.²⁰ Overall, these findings suggest that the increase in income shifting associated with private CbCR is accompanied by greater economic substance in foreign low-tax affiliates. Hence, exposed MNEs respond to private CbCR not only by reducing taxable income in Austria, but also by reallocating economic activity abroad in order to sustain continued income shifting.

Figure 4: Private CbCR - Event Study Estimates for Real Economic Response

Note: This figure plots the annual treatment effects for real economic responses to private CbCR together with their 90% confidence interval. In Panel a (b), the dependent variable is the natural logarithm of the total number of employees (sales) in the jurisdiction of the lowest-taxed foreign affiliate of each Austrian MNE entity. We interact *Treat* with separate year indicators to obtain annual treatment effects. In Panel a (b), these treatment effects capture the difference in total employees (sales) between entities in the treatment group and the control group relative to the year before the introduction of private CbCR (i.e., 2015).

¹⁹Given that affiliate-level data in OFATS is limited to sales and the number of employees, we are unable to control for tangible fixed assets and the cost of employees in the analysis of real economic responses in foreign affiliates.

²⁰In untabulated analyses, we estimate average treatment effects and find a positive and statistically significant increase in employment in foreign low-tax affiliates of treated Austrian MNE entities following the adoption of private CbCR ($\beta = 0.4766$; $p < 0.01$); the change in sales reported by these affiliates is not statistically significant.

5.3 Combined Analysis: Deduction Limitation and Private CbCR

A key advantage of the staggered implementation of the interest and royalty deduction limitation in 2014 and private CbCR in 2016 is that it allows us to examine MNEs' income-shifting responses across both policies and hence assess potential interactions. To do so, we begin with an event-study design and investigate the evolution of income shifting from 2011 until 2018. The treatment group for this analysis consists of Austrian MNE entities classified in Section 4.3 as potentially exposed to both the interest and royalty deduction limitation and private CbCR. To ensure comparability of treatment assignment across the two reforms, we classify Austrian MNE entities as exposed to private CbCR if their lowest-taxed foreign affiliate faces a tax rate of less than 10% in 2015. This approach ensures consistent treatment and control groups throughout the estimation window. We then estimate equation (1) after interacting *Treat* with individual year indicators. Figure 5 visualizes the coefficient estimates and 90% confidence intervals, relative to the base year 2013.

Consistent with the results in Figure 2, exposed Austrian MNE entities exhibit an increase in taxable income relative to the control group following the introduction of the interest and royalty deduction limitation in 2014. After the introduction of private CbCR, however, this effect reverses. Specifically, treated entities experience a decline in taxable income, and by 2018 reported taxable income has returned to pre-2014 levels. This pattern suggests that private CbCR offsets the initial reduction in income shifting induced by the interest and royalty deduction limitation.

Table 8 presents complementary regression results where we estimate average treatment effects for the two reform phases. *Post Deduction Limitation* equals one for 2014–2015 and captures the period following the introduction of the interest and royalty deduction limitation but before private CbCR; *Post CbCR* equals one for 2016–2018 and captures the period after the introduction of private CbCR. Column (1) reports

Figure 5: Combined Analysis - Event Study Estimates for Income-Shifting Response

Note: This figure plots the annual treatment effects for the income-shifting response to the interest and royalty deduction limitation and private CbCR together with their 90% confidence interval. The dependent variable is the natural logarithm of taxable income. We interact *Treat* with separate year indicators to obtain annual treatment estimates. These treatment effects capture the difference in taxable income between entities in the treatment group and the control group relative to the year before the introduction of the interest and royalty deduction limitation (i.e., 2013).

estimates without controls, and we include the full set of controls in column (2). Both specifications include entity and year fixed effects.

The coefficient on $Treat \times Post\ Deduction\ Limitation$ is positive and statistically significant across both specifications, indicating that treated Austrian MNE entities report relatively higher taxable income in the period immediately following the deduction limitation. In contrast, the coefficient on $Treat \times Post\ CbCR$ is insignificant. Hence, the earlier increase in taxable income does not persist after the introduction of private CbCR.

Taken together, these results highlight important interactions between anti-BEPS measures. Targeted restrictions on flexible shifting channels, such as interest and royalty payments, can reduce outward income shifting in the short run. However, broader transparency-based measures such as private CbCR may weaken these effects by inducing incentives to reallocate economic activity to low-tax jurisdictions.

Table 8: Combined Analysis - Income-Shifting Response

	ln(Taxable Income)	
	(1)	(2)
Post Deduction Limitation	0.0650*** (0.0195)	-0.0011 (0.0364)
Treat \times Post Deduction Limitation	0.8407*** (0.2592)	0.4551*** (0.1648)
Post CbCR	0.1906*** (0.0214)	0.0596 (0.0437)
Treat \times Post CbCR	0.1416 (0.2773)	0.1773 (0.2549)
ln(Fixed Assets)		-0.0272 (0.0290)
ln(Costs of Employees)		0.3947*** (0.0797)
Entity FE	Yes	Yes
No. singletons	158	91
Obs.	19,280	3,598
R^2	0.82	0.76

Note: This table presents the results of the analysis of MNEs' income-shifting responses to the 2014 introduction of the interest and royalty deduction limitation and the 2016 introduction of private CbCR. We use the natural logarithm of taxable income as the dependent variable. In column (1), we include no control variables; we include the full set of controls in column (2). All specifications include entity and year fixed effects. We provide detailed variable descriptions in the Appendix. We cluster standard errors by entity. ***, **, and * indicate significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10 % levels.

5.4 CFC Rule

5.4.1 Income-Shifting Response

As a final anti-BEPS measure, we examine MNEs' responses to the 2019 introduction of the CFC rule. We again begin with analyzing MNEs' income-shifting response. To this end, we estimate equation (1) and report the results in Panel A of Table 9. Column (1) presents specifications without control variables while columns (2) through (5) include the full set of controls. Columns (2) and (3) report results for the unmatched sample, and columns (4) and (5) for the propensity-score matched sample.

Across all specifications, the coefficient on $Treat \times Post$ is negative and statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). These results indicate that treated entities report lower

taxable income following the introduction of the CFC rule, consistent with an increase in outward income shifting rather than a reduction. Quantitatively, the estimate in column (4) implies an economically meaningful decline in taxable income of 29%, corresponding to approximately EUR 1.3 million per entity-year at the sample mean.²¹

Panel B presents a placebo test using a pseudo-treatment group of Austrian MNE entities with a *TRD* between 0 and 12.5, i.e., entities whose lowest-taxed foreign affiliate faces a statutory corporate income tax rate above 12.5% (the CFC threshold). Like the primary treatment group, these entities have outward-shifting incentives but are not affected by the CFC rule. Across all specifications, the coefficient on *Treat* \times *Post* is statistically insignificant and economically small, mitigating concerns that differences between entities with inward- and outward-shifting incentives drive our results.

Table 9: CFC Rule - Income-Shifting Response

Panel A: Baseline Analysis					
	ln(Taxable Income)				
	No Controls	Unmatched		Matched	
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
Treat \times Post	-0.3695** (0.1559)	-0.3825** (0.1531)	-0.3873** (0.1779)	-0.3443** (0.1583)	-0.3711** (0.1797)
Treat			0.0971 (0.1279)		0.1000 (0.1186)
ln(Fixed Assets)		-0.0168 (0.0274)	0.1279*** (0.0198)	0.0278 (0.0574)	0.0676** (0.0327)
ln(Costs of Employees)		0.3729*** (0.0631)	0.4003*** (0.0370)	0.2788*** (0.1001)	0.3244*** (0.0650)
Entity FE	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Industry FE	No	No	Yes	No	Yes
No. singletons	142	142	-	61	-
Obs.	2,394	2,394	2,536	2,342	2,403
R^2	0.83	0.84	0.26	0.82	0.26

²¹Computed as $e^{-0.3443} - 1 = -0.2913$.

Panel B: Placebo Analysis

	ln(Taxable Income)				
	No Controls	Unmatched		Matched	
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
Treat \times Post	-0.0165 (0.0697)	-0.0252 (0.0691)	0.0169 (0.0779)	-0.0345 (0.0695)	0.0077 (0.0765)
Treat			-0.1772** (0.0703)		-0.1833** (0.0720)
ln(Fixed Assets)		-0.0260 (0.0261)	0.1233*** (0.0171)	-0.0347 (0.0340)	0.0915*** (0.0200)
ln(Costs of Employees)		0.3536*** (0.0577)	0.4093*** (0.0312)	0.3769*** (0.0666)	0.3963*** (0.0345)
Entity FE	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Industry FE	No	No	Yes	No	Yes
No. singletons	214	214	-	97	-
Obs.	3,141	3,141	3,355	3,066	3,163
R^2	0.82	0.82	0.26	0.81	0.22

Note: This table presents the results of the analysis of MNEs' income-shifting responses to the 2019 introduction of the CFC rule. We perform the baseline analysis in Panel A and a placebo analysis in Panel B. In both panels, we use the natural logarithm of taxable income as the dependent variable. In column (1), we include no control variables. We use an unmatched sample in columns (2) and (3), and a matched sample in columns (4) and (5). We apply kernel-based propensity score matching based on pre-reform characteristics. In columns (1), (2), and (4), we include entity and year fixed effects. In columns (3) and (5), we include industry and year fixed effects. We provide detailed variable descriptions in the Appendix. We cluster standard errors by entity. ***, **, and * indicate significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10 % levels.

Figure 6 again visualizes annual treatment effects from estimating equation (1) within an event-study framework. While taxable income for treated entities exhibits a gradual downward trend relative to the control group before the adoption, we observe a marked additional decline in the adoption year, i.e., 2019. This pattern is consistent with both (i) some pre-existing differential trends in income-shifting behavior and (ii) a sharp behavioral response at the time of implementation. The pronounced reaction in 2019 suggests that exposed MNE entities respond quickly to the CFC rule by reducing the taxable income reported in Austria. It also alleviates concerns that differential trends between treatment and control entities drive our DiD results.

Overall, our evidence suggests that the introduction of the CFC rule is associated with increased outward income shifting rather than the intended reduction. A plausi-

Figure 6: CFC Rule - Event Study Estimates for Income-Shifting Responses

Note: This figure plots the annual treatment effects for MNEs' income-shifting response to the CFC rule together with their 90% confidence interval. The dependent variable is the natural logarithm of taxable income. We interact *Treat* with separate year indicators to obtain annual treatment estimates. These treatment effects capture the difference in taxable income between entities in the treatment group and the control group relative to the year before the introduction of the CFC rule (i.e., 2018).

ble explanation is that the design of the CFC regime, in particular its active-income safe harbor and substance-based exemption, provides certainty about when low-taxed foreign profits will fall outside the scope of the CFC rule. By providing clear boundaries for the applicability of the CFC regime, the policy may have lowered expected enforcement risk and thereby reduced the expected costs of income shifting.

5.4.2 Additional Responses

Income-Shifting Channels

Given that our income-shifting analysis suggests an increase in outward income shifting following the implementation of the CFC rule, we next examine through which shifting channels this response arises. To this end, we estimate equation (2) and report the results in Table 10. Panel A presents results for the unmatched sample, while Panel B reports estimates based on kernel-based propensity score matching.

In Panel A, the coefficient on $Treat \times Post$ is statistically insignificant across all specifications, suggesting no change in income-shifting channels in the unmatched sample. However, in Panel B, we find that treated MNE entities exhibit an increase

in interest expenses and a decrease in royalty payments relative to the control group following the introduction of the CFC rule. The estimates imply an economically large increase in interest expenses of approximately EUR 12 million per entity-year and a decline in royalty payments of approximately EUR 2.5 million per entity-year, evaluated at the respective sample means. These results suggest a shift in the composition of income-shifting strategies away from royalties toward interest payments.

This pattern is notable given that the CFC rule was designed to restrict the outflow of passive income, including interest payments, to low-tax jurisdictions. Hence, our findings indicate that, rather than curbing such outflows, the policy is associated with an expansion of interest-based shifting. A potential reason is that MNEs strategically exploit the active-income safe harbor or the substance-based exemption, which may allow them to stay outside the scope of the rule and expand intra-group financing structures. We explore this mechanism in the next section.

Table 10: CFC Rule - Income-Shifting Channels

Panel A: Unmatched Sample				
	$\ln(\text{EBIT})$	$\ln(\text{Interest})$	$\ln(\text{Debt})$	$\ln(\text{Royalty Payments})$
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
Treat \times Post	-0.0729 (0.0537)	0.3593 (0.3308)	0.0134 (0.3863)	0.0965 (0.1279)
$\ln(\text{Fixed Assets})$	0.0239 (0.0194)	0.1277 (0.0816)	0.1635 (0.1333)	0.0491 (0.0352)
$\ln(\text{Costs of Employees})$	0.3240*** (0.0678)	0.0657 (0.2627)	0.2833 (0.2179)	0.5523*** (0.0666)
Entity FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
No. singletons	142	73	137	6
Obs.	2,394	1,813	1,078	1,016
R^2	0.95	0.83	0.71	0.96

Panel B: Matched Sample				
	ln(EBIT)	ln(Interest)	ln(Debt)	ln(Royalty Payments)
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
Treat \times Post	-0.0372 (0.0809)	2.5338** (1.1539)	-0.6214 (1.1530)	-0.3203** (0.1401)
ln(Fixed Assets)	0.1337* (0.0734)	-0.0298 (0.1428)	0.3501* (0.1812)	0.0640 (0.0570)
ln(Costs of Employees)	0.3147*** (0.0900)	-0.7398* (0.4242)	-0.1414 (0.4261)	0.4348** (0.1739)
Entity FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
No. singletons	31	58	110	1
Obs.	1,984	1,476	857	828
R^2	0.95	0.83	0.72	0.98

Note: This table presents the results of the analysis of alternative responses to the 2019 introduction of the CFC rule, focusing on income-shifting channels. Column (1) uses the natural logarithm of modified EBIT as the dependent variable; columns (2) and (3) use the natural logarithms of interest expenses and long-term debt, respectively; and column (4) uses the natural logarithm of royalty payments. Panel A reports the results for the unmatched sample, and Panel B reports results for the matched sample. We apply kernel-based propensity score matching based on pre-reform characteristics. All specifications include entity and year fixed effects. We provide detailed variable descriptions in the Appendix. We cluster standard errors by entity. ***, **, and * indicate significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10 % levels.

Real Economic Responses

As noted above, MNEs exposed to the CFC rule may respond by adjusting economic activity in foreign jurisdictions in order to meet activity- or substance-based exemptions and avoid the application of the rule. To test for this mechanism, we follow the approach used in the analysis of private CbCR and aggregate sales and employment for affiliates located in the jurisdiction of the Austrian MNE entity's lowest-taxed foreign affiliate. We then use the natural logarithm of these measures as dependent variables in equation (1) and estimate the model in an event-study framework.

Figure 7, Panels (a) and (b) report annual treatment effects using foreign employment as the outcome variable. Panel (a) provides suggestive evidence of a modest increase in employment in foreign low-tax affiliates of treated Austrian MNE entities following the introduction of the CFC rule. However, the estimate is not statistically significant at conventional levels, likely reflecting limited statistical power due to the

relatively small sample size and incomplete coverage of employment in the OFATS data. Consistent with this interpretation, using the placebo-treatment group in Panel (b) yields no effect. In Panels (c) and (d), we repeat the analysis using sales as the outcome variable. In Panel (c), we observe a relative increase in sales reported by foreign low-tax affiliates of treated Austrian MNE entities following the implementation of the CFC rule ($p = 0.14$).²² The placebo specification in Panel (d) again suggests no change in sales, supporting the validity of our initial result.

Taken together, our evidence is consistent with an increase in economic activity in foreign low-tax affiliates following the introduction of the CFC rule. Specifically, exposed MNEs appear to adjust the composition of activity within their foreign affiliates to satisfy the active-income safe harbor, which excludes foreign affiliates from the CFC regime if their passive income does not exceed one-third of total income. By increasing sales reported in foreign low-tax affiliates, MNEs increase the share of active income and reduce the likelihood that the CFC rule applies. By introducing such clear thresholds for applicability, the Austrian CFC rule may have provided greater certainty for tax planning, ultimately facilitating rather than constraining income shifting.

²²In untabulated analyses, we estimate average treatment effects. The estimated coefficient on $Treat \times Post$ is not statistically significant for either employment or sales.

Figure 7: CFC Rule - Event Study Estimates for Real Economic Responses

Note: This figure plots annual treatment effects for real economic responses to the CFC rule together with their 90% confidence interval. In Panels (a) and (b), the dependent variable is the natural logarithm of the total number of employees in the jurisdiction of the lowest-taxed foreign affiliate of each Austrian MNE entity in our sample. In Panels (c) and (d), the dependent variable is the natural logarithm of total sales reported in the jurisdiction of the lowest-taxed foreign affiliate of each Austrian MNE entity in our sample. We interact *Treat* with separate year indicators to obtain annual treatment effects. In Panels (a) and (c) we use the CFC rule-based treatment definition described in Section 4.3. In Panels (b) and (d), we define a placebo-treatment group. We compute annual treatment effects relative to the year before the introduction of the CFC rule (i.e., 2018).

6 Conclusion

This study analyzes MNEs' responses to three major anti-BEPS measures: (i) limitations on the deductibility of interest and royalty payments, (ii) private CbCR, and (iii) CFC rules. Using Austrian administrative corporate tax return data, we show that, depending on their design, anti-BEPS measures have distinct and nuanced effects. Targeted measures limiting the deductibility of intra-group interest and royalty payments significantly reduce income shifting out of Austria without inducing meaningful substitution toward alternative shifting channels. In contrast, broader transparency-based measures and those providing activity-based carve-outs, such as CFC rules, are less

effective in constraining income shifting. In fact, following the introduction of private CbCR and the CFC rule, exposed MNEs increase economic activity in low-tax jurisdictions, which allows them to maintain or even increase income shifting.

Our findings contribute to the growing literature on MNEs' responses to anti-BEPS policies (Joshi et al., 2020; Clifford, 2019; Nessa et al., 2025; Saunders-Scott, 2015) by showing that evaluating individual measures in isolation can provide an incomplete picture of how MNEs respond to international tax reform. Specifically, while some anti-BEPS measures effectively constrain specific shifting channels, others provide incentives to adjust economic activity in low-tax jurisdictions. More broadly, these findings suggest that anti-BEPS measures can generate distortions in firms' real economic activity while not necessarily reducing the overall level of income shifting. Our findings have important implications for the design of future international tax policy, including ongoing efforts to implement the global minimum tax and recent proposals to simplify the EU's anti-BEPS framework (EU Commission, 2026).

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A Appendix

A.1 Variable Definitions

	Description	Source
Dependent Variables		
Taxable Income	Taxable income as reported in the corporate income tax return (kz2605, “Einkünfte aus Gewerbebetrieb”).	AMDC
EBIT	Sum of taxable income as reported in the corporate income tax return (kz2605) plus interest expenses (interest_paid) and other operating expenses as reported in the financial statements (“Übriger betrieblicher Aufwand”).	AMDC /Orbis
Interest	Interest expenses as reported in the financial statements (interest_paid).	Orbis
Debt	Long-term debt as reported in the financial statements (long_term_debt).	Orbis
Royalty Payments	Other operating expenses as reported in the financial statements (“Übriger betrieblicher Aufwand”).	Sabina
Employees	Aggregated number of employees across all affiliates located in the jurisdiction of the entity’s lowest-taxed foreign affiliate.	AMDC
Sales	Aggregated sales across all affiliates located in the jurisdiction of the entity’s lowest-taxed foreign affiliate.	AMDC

Main Independent Variables

Treat	Indicator variable equal to one if the lowest-taxed foreign affiliate is subject to a statutory corporate income tax rate below the respective low-tax threshold for a given anti-BEPS measure, and zero otherwise. For the private CbCR analysis, the indicator variable is equal to one if the lowest-taxed foreign affiliate is located in a tax haven. The indicator variable is zero if the tax rate differential is negative.	Own calculations
Post	Indicator variable equal to one if an entity-year observation falls into the respective post-reform period, and zero otherwise.	Own calculations
Post CbCR	Indicator variable equal to one for the years 2016-2018, and zero for the years 2011-2015, respectively.	Own calculations
Post Deduction Limitation	Indicator variable equal to one for the years 2014 and 2015, and zero for the years 2011-2013 and 2016-2018, respectively.	Own calculations
Tax Rate Differential	Maximum statutory corporate income tax rate differential for a given Austrian MNE entity in percentage points, defined as the Austrian statutory corporate income tax rate (25% throughout our sample period) less the lowest foreign statutory corporate income tax rate within the MNE group in a given year.	Tax Foundation/AMDC

Control Variables

Fixed Assets	Fixed assets as reported in the financial statements (fixed_assets).	Orbis
Cost of Employees	Cost of employees as reported in the financial statements (costs_of_employees).	Orbis
